

EXPLORING STUDENTS' EXPERIENCES IN THE UTILIZATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The global outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic affects all aspects of life, including education, causing a shift in our idea of what education looks like. Virtual learning platforms are introduced. Digital technology has significantly improved the teaching-learning process. Digital technologies and tools are advantageous in a variety of ways. The educational establishments recognized the value of digital tools and artificial intelligence in improving the teaching-learning experience. The researcher will explore deeper into the students' experience's in the utilization of digital tools. This study surveyed 64 Grade 10 students at Gallanosa National High School in Irosin, Sorsogon, using a descriptive method. The questionnaire underwent validity checks and data analysis using descriptive statistics such as percentage, ranking, average weighted mean, over-all weighted mean, and the 4-point Likert scale. Digital tools in education have revolutionized learning by providing access to vast information, simplifying lesson creation, aiding knowledge acquisition, and increasing productivity. They enhance self-concept and character development through expressive skills and communication. However, they also pose drawbacks like technostress, mental exhaustion, burnout, and high costs. Understanding these impacts is crucial for academic success and overall well-being. Digital tools can foster caution and camaraderie among diverse cultures, but also impatience and entitlement. They also help prevent cyberbullying and promote self-expression. Despite these benefits, it's crucial to mitigate their negative impacts. Digital literacy is crucial for students and educators, addressing societal factors and developmental needs. It covers computer functions, online communication, digital safety, and information literacy, improving success in school, work, and society.

Keywords: *Digital Tools, Digital Technology, Artificial Intelligence, Technostress*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused major disruptions in education in the Philippines, affecting millions of learners. Traditional educational practices have been significantly disturbed by social distancing and restrictive movement policies. Teachers are adapting to new strategies to meet required competencies, resulting in drastic changes in the education sector. Despite this, technology has become a silver lining in the education system, as it allows learners to access education through different modalities. Online lessons, mobile devices, and digital learning have become the norm.

Virtual learning platforms enable teachers to provide high-quality online education through video conferencing, slide displays, and online whiteboards. These collaborative environments allow students to communicate in breakout rooms and receive timely feedback. Despite the growth of virtual learning in 2020, educators have faced challenges due to the need for more time to use technology. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has significantly improved teaching-learning, with academic administration, teaching, and student learning now centered around technology. Educational establishments recognize the value of digital tools and artificial intelligence in improving the teaching-learning experience.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize education by analyzing student performance data, providing targeted support, and personalizing learning. It can also assist teachers with administrative tasks, freeing up time for teaching. However, ethical concerns include data privacy and potential bias. As AI technology advances, it is crucial to consider both benefits and risks before implementing it in schools. The pandemic has highlighted the necessity of online teaching, leading to increased use of digital tools. As a teacher, the researcher believes studying students' experiences with digital tools can help alleviate potential negative aspects.

Research Questions

The researcher would like to know in detail the experiences of students' in utilization of digital tools.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the varied digital tools used by Grade 10 students in learning?
2. What is the extent of utilization of the varied digital tools by the Grade 10 students:
 - 2.1 knowledge acquisition
 - 2.2 self-concept and character development
 - 2.3 Intra and interpersonal engagement

3. What are the advantages and disadvantages in using digital technology as assessed by students?
4. How does the utilization of digital tools affect students:
 - 4.1 knowledge acquisition
 - 4.2 self-concept and character development
 - 4.3 intra and interpersonal engagement
5. What digital literacy modules may be proposed to guide the students in the utilization of digital tools?

METHODOLOGY

The locale of the study is Gallanosa National High School in the municipality of Irosin, Sorsogon. Other schools in the nearby vicinity were not included in this study. Sixty-four students from the Grade 10 STE program, were the respondents in this study. The study was conducted from November to January of the School Year 2022- 2023. This study excluded students from other grade levels. This did not cover the months and years before and after the abovementioned timeline. The study used the descriptive method which aims to describe or summarize a phenomenon or group of phenomena without manipulating or altering them. A Survey questionnaire or checklist was the main instrument used in measuring the experiences of students in the utilization of digital tools. The questionnaire consisted of two significant parts. Part A reflected the items about the varied tools used by the students in learning. Part B, on the other hand, included items that have a bearing on the extent of the utilization of the varied digital tools by the Grade 10 students along with knowledge acquisition, self-concept, character development, and intra and interpersonal engagement of the students. The questionnaire passed through a validity check with the help of the researcher's adviser and the statistician. The data were collected, categorized, and prepared for the analysis. To ensure the accuracy of the results and its findings, the research had to use descriptive statistics. The statistical treatment used in this study were percentage, ranking, average weighted mean, over-all weighted mean and the 4-point Likert scale.

RESULTS

TABLE 1
DIGITAL TOOLS USED IN LEARNING

Digital Tools	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Search Engines (Chrome, Bing, Mozilla, etc.)	64	100
Office 365 (Word, Excel, Powerpoint, etc.)	64	100
Social Media (Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, etc.)	64	100
Messaging Applications (Messenger, Viber, etc.)	64	100

Graphic Design (Canva, Adobe, etc)	64	100
Productivity (Notes, Calculator, Whiteboards, etc)	64	100
Streaming Applications (Youtube, Netflix, etc.)	64	100
Email (Gmail, Yahoo, etc.)	64	100

TABLE 2.1
THE EXTENT OF UTILIZATION OF VARIED DIGITAL TOOLS ALONG
KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Digital tools are utilized to complete projects and assignments.	3.53	Highly Utilized
Digital tools provide more information.	3.33	Utilized
Digital tools help learners in becoming more productive in school.	3.03	Utilized
Digital tools provide an accessible reading materials.	2.97	Utilized
Digital tools provide different streaming apps for learning.	2.56	Utilized
Digital tools help students to avoid plagiarism.	2.03	Slightly Utilized
Average Weighted Mean	2.90	UTILIZED

TABLE 2.2
THE EXTENT OF UTILIZATION OF VARIED DIGITAL TOOLS ALONG
SELF-CONCEPT AND CHARACTER DEVELOPMENT

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Digital tools facilitate in expressing oneself.	3.06	Utilized
Digital tools serve as a channel to update others about oneself	2.38	Slightly Utilized
Digital tools are utilized to get the attention needed online.	2.36	Slightly Utilized
Digital tools are used to prevent online impersonation.	2.20	Slightly Utilized
Average Weighted Mean	2.50	UTILIZED

TABLE 2.3
THE EXTENT OF UTILIZATION OF VARIED DIGITAL TOOLS ALONG
INTRA AND INTERPERSONAL ENGAGEMENT

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Digital tools are used for communication	3.61	Highly Utilized
Digital tools have made it easier to have more friends.	2.59	Utilized
Digital tools are utilized to have a quality conversation.	2.36	Slightly Utilized
Digital tools are utilized in order to leave comments to the post or work of others.	2.25	Slightly Utilized
Digital tools are used to avoid online manipulation.	1.80	Slightly Utilized
Average Weighted Mean	2.52	UTILIZED

TABLE 3.1
ADVANTAGE IN USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AS ASSESSED BY THE
STUDENTS

Indicators	Frequency	Rank
Digital technology provides things that interest learners	62	1
Digital technology improves the quality of work.	60	3
Personalizes teaching and learning process.	60	3
Supports critical aspects of studies.	60	3
Enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly	59	5
Digital tools save time.	55	6
Allows to accomplish more work than would otherwise be possible.	52	7
Boost communication and teamwork.	50	8
My effectiveness on class is enhanced by digital tools.	48	9
Digital tools increase my productivity.	43	10

TABLE 3.2
DISADVANTAGE IN USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AS ASSESSED BY THE
STUDENTS

Indicators	Frequency	Rank
Technology causes technostress, mental exhaustion and burn-outs	56	1
Limited access on digital tools because of its cost	52	2
Causes distractions and concentration problems	50	3
Digital technology invaded my personal life	33	4
Spend less time with family due to this technology.	32	5

Digital technology complexity cause higher workload.	31	6
Not enough time to study and upgrade technology skills.	24	7
Sacrifice vacation and weekend time to keep current on new technologies.	17	8

TABLE 4.1
UTILIZATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS AFFECTS THE STUDENTS ALONG
KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

Knowledge Acquisition	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Digital tools help learner to acquire knowledge necessary for their teaching and learning engagement.	3.63	Strongly Agree
Digital tools provide the students a wide range of learning opportunity about academics and life-supporting documentaries.	3.22	Agree
Digital tools users are provided with so much information.	3.14	Agree
Learners become more critical thinker upon using media.	3.03	Agree
Learners become more convinced of the information from digital tools.	3.00	Agree
Digital tools enhance communication skills.	2.91	Agree
The more the students are engage in digital tools the more the chance of being aware of the reality and good practices in life.	2.73	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.09	AGREE

TABLE 4.2
HOW UTILIZATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS AFFECTS THE STUDENTS ALONG SELF-
CONCEPT AND CHARACTER DEVELOPMENT

Self-concept and Character development	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
There are information from digital tools that affects the character traits innate among learners (such as pranking, challenges, fame and the likes)	3.50	Strongly Agree
Students become more cautious of their actions.	3.03	Agree
Digital tools are efficient in developing camaraderie among students with varied culture.	2.97	Agree
Digital tools cause students to develop proper communication skills.	2.94	Agree
Digital tools developed credibility among students.	2.89	Agree
Students developed time management	2.78	Agree
Digital tools strengthen one's personality.	2.75	Agree

Digital tools boost the confidence and self-esteem of the students.	2.70	Agree
Digital tools increases the learner's curiosity	2.67	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	2.91	AGREE

TABLE 4.3
HOW UTILIZATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS AFFECTS THE STUDENTS ALONG INTRA AND INTERPERSONAL ENGAGEMENT

Intra and Interpersonal engagement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
Digital tools prevent cyberbullying.	3.50	Strongly Agree
Digital tools developed security to avoid scams and phishing.	3.31	Agree
Digital tools provide an opportunity to express oneself.	3.16	Agree
Digital tools users become more considerate in dealing with people.	2.97	Agree
Digital tools create communities not markets.	2.94	Agree
Students turn out to be more patient in handling their emotional struggles due to online support.	2.86	Agree
Students hold longer and quality conversation.	2.52	Agree
A smooth relationship among users of digital tools is established.	2.48	Disagree
Average Weighted Mean	3.00	AGREE

DISCUSSION

The results in table no.1 shows that all the respondents use varied digital tools in their learning. Digital tools let students access a vast amount of information with just a few clicks. They can easily search for information on the internet, download e-books, and take online courses. This ease of access to information has transformed the way students learn and has made it easier for them to research and complete assignments. Brenner (2020) stated that there is an increase in technology available in classrooms, and more teachers and students are using digital learning tools than ever before. Many of these tools can simplify lesson creation and management, and improve engagement and discussion for students. Using digital learning tools can increase students' time learning and can be very effective.

Table 2.1 reveals that along with knowledge acquisition, the respondents use varied digital tools to complete assignments and projects. Digital tools are also being used by the respondents in getting more information and aid to become more productive in school.

Raja (2018) stated that the internet has grown in importance by many folds, over the process of decade. Its importance in the education world can never be undermined. The use of the internet allows students to find amazing convenience, they can find various kinds of help, tutorials and other kinds of assisting material that could be used to academically improve and enhance their learning.

Table 2.2 reveals the extent of utilization of varied digital tools along self-concept and character development, the respondents use varied digital tools to express themselves. Bulut and Delen (2011) which stated that the online learning environment is perfect for integrating multimodal forms of expression. Digital tools allow students to develop their expressive skills and demonstrate what they know using text, photos, graphics, audio, and video.

Likewise, table 2.3 reveals the extent of utilization of varied digital tools along intra and interpersonal engagement, respondents preference for communicating is through digital tools rather than using the traditional way of communicating such as writing and that the digital tools are also being utilized by the respondents to have more friends. Bulut and Delen (2011) stated that struggling writers and language learners can benefit from multimodal ways to express themselves. For students with disabilities, digital tools can provide scaffolds that help students demonstrate what they have learned. If an assignment requires students to write, you can use multimodal options to help them develop what they will eventually write. They can express themselves using slides, audio, and video and use those multimodal pieces to develop longer pieces in different formats if needed.

The assessment of learners in the advantage of using digital technology shows that that digital technology helps the respondents to find things that interest them. Another positive experience of respondents in using digital technology improves the quality of the student's work, personalizes the teaching and learning process, and supports the critical aspects of the learner's studies. The data in table 3.1 shows that digital technology has opened up a world of possibilities for students who are looking to explore their interests and deepen their understanding of the world around them. D'Angelo (2018) stated that student motivation and engagement in learning are enhanced by the implementation of instructional technology. More specifically, digital technology engages students behaviorally, emotionally, and cognitively.

On the other table 3.2 presents the disadvantages of using digital technology as assessed by the students. Digital technology has drawbacks. Digital technology causes technostress, mental exhaustion, and burnout. Another disadvantage is the high cost of digital technology which causes the limited access of the respondents. The cost of digital technology can be a significant burden for students, particularly those from lower-income households. As technology becomes more integral to education, students are often expected to have access to laptops, tablets, and other devices in order to complete assignments and stay connected with their teachers and classmates. However, these devices can be expensive, and the cost of software and internet access can add up quickly. The research entitled, *The Effect of Technostress in the Academic Performance*

of *G10 Virtual Students in Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao* (2023) stated that technostress causes concentration problems and it is a very serious concern. Technostress can cause mental exhaustion and burnout, memory difficulty and fatigue, and physiological concerns, such as lack of sleep and social interaction. Technostress can also cause anxiety and depression disorder. A decrease in productivity may be seen as one of the effects of technostress.

Table 4.1 shows how the utilization of digital tools affects the students' knowledge acquisition. It shows that digital tools help the respondents to acquire the knowledge necessary for their teaching and learning engagement. Digital tools also provide students with a wide range of learning opportunities about academics and life-supporting documentaries. In addition, digital tools users are provided with too much information that may lead to confusion. Lei and Zhao (2007) stated that spending some time on computers may help students increase their learning outcomes, but too much time on computers can be harmful.

Similarly, along self-concept and character development, the table 4.2 shows that there is information from digital tools that affects the character traits innate among learners. The utilization of digital tools makes the students more cautious of their actions. In addition, digital tools are efficient in developing camaraderie among students with varied cultures. Understanding the effects digital tools have on a student's self-concept and character development is vital. Ensuring that students use these tools in a healthy and balanced way is crucial to their academic success and overall well-being. The study conducted by Storey (2010) claimed that digital tools harm our character development. One of the biggest drawbacks of technology is that it has made us more isolated and less social. With the advent of social media and messaging apps, we no longer need to physically interact with others to stay in touch. This has resulted in a decrease in face-to-face communication, making it harder for us to develop social skills and form meaningful relationships. Another negative impact of technology on character development is that it has made us more impatient and entitled.

Moreover, along Intra and Interpersonal engagement, table 4.3 shows that digital tools help in preventing cyberbullying. Other notable results from the table show that digital tools developed security to avoid scams and phishing, and that digital tools provide an opportunity to express oneself. This data shows that digital tools influence the intra and interpersonal engagement of learners. Online bullying and deception are serious issues that can have a profound impact on individuals and society as a whole. Bhat (2017) in her study stated that digital tools play a crucial role in preventing cyberbullying. With the rise of social media and online communication, cyberbullying has become a prevalent issue, particularly among young people. However, technology has also provided solutions to this problem.

While technology has undoubtedly brought many benefits, it is important to be mindful of its negative impacts on our students and take steps to mitigate them. The integration of digital tools in education is essential to preparing students for success in the modern world. By providing access to information, fostering self-concept and character

development, and promoting intra and interpersonal engagement, digital tools can have a profound impact on student learning and growth.

Conclusions

The varied digital tools used by the learners in learning are search engines, office 365, social media, messaging applications, graphic designs, productivity applications, streaming applications and e-mail. Digital tools have become an essential part of students' studies. They have revolutionized the way students learn by providing easy access to information, more interactive learning experiences, and collaboration opportunities. As technology continues to advance, we can expect more innovative digital tools to emerge and improve the learning experience even further.

The use of digital tools in education has a positive impact on the knowledge acquisition of students. These tools provide students with access to a vast array of resources, allow them to learn at their own pace, and help them develop their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. As technology continues to advance, educators need to incorporate digital tools into their teaching practices. It is undeniable that digital tools such as social media and online forums have an impact on the self-concept and character development of students. On one hand, these tools can provide a platform for students to express themselves and connect with others who share similar interests. This can be a positive influence on their self-concept, as they may feel validated and accepted by their online community. The rise of digital tools in classrooms has changed the way students interact with one another and with their teachers. These tools have made it easier for students to collaborate and communicate with each other, both in-person and remotely. However, they have also led to a shift in the way students engage with each other and with the learning process itself.

Digital technology has become an indispensable aspect of student life in today's world. It has revolutionized the way students learn and communicate. The introduction of digital technology has made it easier for students to access information and resources online, thereby streamlining the learning process. One of the most prominent advantages of digital technology in students' lives is its ability to provide access to a vast amount of information. Online libraries, journals, and databases have made research more manageable, thereby enhancing the writing of essays and research papers. Moreover, digital technology has transformed the way students communicate with their peers and teachers. Messaging apps, social media platforms, and email have made communication between students and teachers more accessible, facilitating collaboration on group projects. However, the use of digital technology can also pose certain challenges. It can be a source of distraction for students, making it challenging for them to concentrate on their studies. Additionally, students may become overly reliant on technology, potentially hindering their ability to think critically and solve problems independently.

The use of digital tools in education has both positive and negative impacts on students' knowledge acquisition. While digital tools offer a wealth of resources and promote

collaboration, students must also be mindful of their over-reliance on technology and the potential for confusion and distractions. Educators need to strike a balance between the use of digital tools and traditional teaching methods to ensure that students receive a well-rounded education. Understanding the effects digital tools have on a student's self-concept and character development is vital. Character development is another area that can be positively impacted by digital tools in education. These tools can promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as well as decision-making, creativity, and leadership skills. Ensuring that students use these tools in a healthy and balanced way is crucial to their academic success and overall well-being. Lastly, digital tools can enhance intrapersonal and interpersonal engagement among students. With the ability to collaborate and communicate with their peers, students can build a sense of community within the classroom. This leads to increased motivation, engagement, and overall satisfaction with the learning experience.

The K to 12 curriculum emphasizes capacitating learners with skills in doing their tasks and enriching these as they progress up to Grade 12. The curriculum takes into account societal factors and the learner's developmental needs. They need to perform different tasks, confront personal and social issues, and eventually decide on their curriculum exit. A responsive and proactive program in addition to the existing academic programs must address these needs. With the goal for learners to keep up with the ever-changing world of technology, a Digital Literacy Program must be introduced. Digital literacy is a vital skill set for students and educators alike. As one of the most important skills in the modern workplace, the importance of digital literacy for student success cannot be understated. Digital literacy is becoming increasingly important in our modern world. As we rely more and more on technology in our personal and professional lives, we must have the skills and knowledge needed to use it effectively. The digital literacy module covers a range of topics, including basic computer functions, online communication and collaboration, digital safety and security, and information literacy. By developing these skills, individuals can improve their ability to succeed in school, work, and life in general. Additionally, digital literacy is crucial for participating in and contributing to society, as many aspects of modern life require some level of technical proficiency. The said Digital Literacy Program will be in the form of a module that will be integrated across the academic curriculum and during Homeroom Guidance classes.

Recommendations

Based on the aforementioned conclusions, the following recommendations were formulated:

1. Choose the right digital tools for your needs. Consider factors such as the task at hand, the level of technical proficiency, and the features offered by the tool. Be sure to also prioritize data privacy and security by using reputable and trustworthy tools.

2. Continue the responsible usage of different digital tools in accomplishing different school outputs but without setting aside social skills. The following steps are recommended: (a) Set aside time for face-to-face interactions with friends and family. (b) Practice active listening when communicating digitally. (c) Use video conferencing tools when possible to maintain nonverbal communication. (d) Join online communities or groups that align with your interests to connect with like-minded individuals. (e) Be mindful of your digital etiquette, such as using appropriate language and responding promptly and (f) Take breaks from technology to engage in activities that promote social interaction, such as going for a walk or attending a social event.
3. Strengthen digital literacy at school and home, there are a few steps we can take. First, make sure that both teachers and parents are well-informed about digital tools and resources available for students. Encourage the use of technology in the classroom and at home, and guide safe and responsible online behavior. Additionally, offers workshops and training sessions for both teachers and parents on digital literacy skills. Finally, incorporate digital literacy into the curriculum, making it a part of everyday learning.
4. Be a digital citizen. Becoming a digital citizen involves learning about and practicing responsible and safe behavior online. This includes being mindful of your online activity, respecting the privacy of others, and being aware of potential online threats such as cyberbullying and scams. It is also important to stay informed about current events and issues related to the digital world.
5. The proposed digital literacy module be adopted.
6. Future studies be conducted with the following suggested topics:
 - The Level of Implementation of DepEd's Digital Rise Program
 - The Level of Digital Citizenship of Teachers
 - The Effects of Technostress on the Academic Performance of Students

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before the actual data-gathering activity, the researchers sought the approval of the conduct of the study from the different authorities as well as from the respondents of this study. In the letter sent for approval, the researcher mentioned that their consent to conduct the study was indeed essential and would play a significant role in realizing the goals of this present study. Before the actual conduct of the study, it was ensured that due permission was sought from the different involved individuals and institutions. Such approval led this present study to gather the pertinent data smoothly, appropriately, and officially. Also, the researcher guaranteed to the school officials that no time or work disturbances could happen during the data gathering activities and followed all public health and safety regulations to ensure the protection of well-being.

Aside from the consent sought to conduct the study, the researcher also guaranteed the confidentiality of the disclosed data of the respondents. In the Google Form provided, it asked for the respondent's name on an optional basis only. Since the data was mainly about the respondent's personal experiences, the researcher was careful about the confidentiality of any disclosed data and information. In the last part of the questionnaire encoded in the Google Form, the researcher stated the confidentiality of any disclosed information by the respondents.

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